

2. LMPCR fingerprints of representative Xoo isolates. Letters denote IS1113-based restriction fragment length polymorphism groupings. Lane c, no template control; and lane m, molecular weight markers.

of PCR (1 min denaturation at 94 °C, 1 min annealing at 62 °C, and 2 min extension at 72 °C) and a final extension for 7 min at 72 °C using a Perkin Elmer Cetus DNA thermal cycler. The products were visualized in a gel containing 0.5% agarose and 0.75% Synergel™ (Diversified Biotech, Newton, MA, USA) after staining with ethidium bromide.

Using this method, bands were amplified from *Eco*RI-digested and ligated Xoo DNA. No bands were amplified from the undigested DNA or from the digested and unligated DNA

controls. The Xoo DNA fingerprints consisted of 1-7 amplified fragments, ranging in size from 250 bp to 1.3 kbp long (Fig. 2).

While LMPCR generated consistent and reproducible fingerprints for Xoo, it yielded only a single 2.5-kbp band in 4 of the 29 isolates of Xocola tested. Furthermore, this single band or another higher molecular weight band was more frequently seen in the digested but unligated Xocola DNA controls. LMPCR of four DNA samples each from *Oryza sativa*, *Magnaporthe grisea*, and *Pseudomonas*

sp. yielded no bands. Southern hybridization of *Eco*RI-digested DNA using IS1113 as a probe confirmed the absence of IS1113 sequences in these samples.

Visual inspection of the LMPCR fingerprints of 74 Xoo isolates showed a good correspondence with their groupings using IS1113-based restriction fragment length polymorphism patterns (Fig. 2). This study shows that LMPCR has potential as an alternative strategy for fingerprinting Xoo isolates and as a diagnostic tool for differentiating Xoo from Xocola. ■

Primers for the amplification of rice tungro bacilliform virus DNA genome by polymerase chain reaction

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The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique allows the amplification and rapid recovery of specific viral sequences from complex mixtures of DNA derived from infected host plant or viruliferous insect vectors. Optimization of individual reaction component quality and concentrations (Taq polymerase, MgCl₂, template DNA, and primers) as well as optimization of temperature and time profiles are necessary to ensure the best reproducibility and efficiency of PCR.

We designed 11 sets of 20-mer primers according to the published sequence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV). Antisense primer and sense primer of all adjacent primer sets overlapped each other. PCR conditions were optimized to amplify 11 overlapping DNA fragments that covered 100% of RTBV DNA genome (see table).

The total nucleic acid extract was prepared by grinding 2 to 3-cm-long infected leaf pieces in a mortar and pestle containing 2X CTAB buffer plus traces of 2-mercaptoethanol. After grinding, the samples were extracted with chloroform-isoamyl alcohol mixture and precipitated with 70% isopropanol at -20 °C for 2 h. DNA pellets were oven-dried and suspended in TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl + 1 mM EDTA, pH 8). For PCR amplifi-

cation, about 100 mg of total nucleic acid extract of leaf tissue was incubated in a thin-walled Gene Amp reaction tube containing 1X PCR buffer (50 mM KCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3), 2.5 units (0.5 µl) Taq polymerase, 0.5 µM each of two primers, 0.2 mM of each dNTPs, and 4 mM MgCl₂ in a total reaction volume of 100 µl. The PCR products were analyzed with an ethidium bromide-stained 2% agarose gel in 1X TBE buffer using two size markers, one ranging from 50 bp to 1000 bp and the other from 1000 bp to 3000 bp. Except for primer sets 3, 4, and 7, all PCR amplifications were carried out for 40 cycles with a denaturation temperature of 94 °C for 1 min, annealing temperature of 53 °C for 2 min and extension temperature of 72 °C for 3 min, followed by final extension tem-

Primer sets for the amplification of RTBV DNA.

Sequence sense and antisense	Amplifying region (bp positions)	PCR product size (bp)
Set 1 5'-TGGTATCAGAGCGATGTTTCG-3' 5'-TCAGAGGTTGAATCTTGGGT-3'	1-1052	1052
Set 2 5'-AGTGAAGTAGTTCAGCAGG-3' 5'-TTCATCCCATCTAGGTGTG-3'	893-1740	848
Set 3 5'-GCCGGTTGTGGAGTGTCTA-3' 5'-TCTACCATCCATCCAAGACC-3'	1471-2718	1248
Set 4 5'-GGTCTGGATGGATGGTAGA-3' 5'-GCTGAGGTGCTACATAGGTT-3'	2669-4165	1467
Set 5 5'-CCTGTGAAACCAATACTGC-3' 5'-ATGCTGCTGTTCTATGCCTG-3'	3596-4669	1074
Set 6 5'-CAACAGCCAGACACGAACCT-3' 5'-CCAGCCTTCTCTGACGCAT-3'	4271-5481	1211
Set 7 5'-CAGATGCGTCAGAAGAAGGC-3' 5'-CAGTCCAGTATCCAGCTTCA-3'	5459-6612	1154
Set 8 5'-AGAGTGCCTAACTAAGGTCG-3' 5'-TGTGGTGCAGGACATTGTGT-3'	6011-7169	1159
Set 9 5'-CCTCGCTGGAACCTCAATGA-3' 5'-AAGACGACTACTCACTGACC-3'	6888-7522	635
Set 10 5'-CAAGGTTCTGAAGGGCTAC-3' 5'-TTGGTATCCACACTAGCAGA-3'	6794-7891	1098
Set 11 5'-GTACCGTCAGGCCGTGTTAT-3' 5'-GCTCCTGCTGAACTACTTCC-3'	7718-915	1200

PCR products resolved in 2% agarose gel, stained with ethidium bromide, and visualized by UV illumination. Lanes 1 and 13 = size markers (100-300 bp and 1000-3000 bp), respectively; lanes 2-12 = PCR products produced from amplification reactions using 11 primer sets (primer set 1 to primer set 11).

perature of 72 °C for 6 min. For primer sets 3, 4, and 7, amplifications were carried out for 38 cycles with a denaturation temperature of 94 °C for 1 min, annealing temperature of 43 °C for 1 min, and extension temperature of 72 °C for 5 min. A 50 µl oil overlay was used to prevent refluxing of the sample. Total nucleic acid extracts from infected and uninfected rice leaves were used as positive and negative controls, respectively, and examined by agarose gel electrophoresis.

Results of the amplification, the corresponding PCR products derived by using each primer set, are shown in the figure. Using these 11 sets of primers, we are now able to amplify any part of the RTBV genome from tungro-infected plant DNA extract. ■

Clonal propagation of thermosensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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A simple and reliable technique for clonal propagation of thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was developed. Mature seeds (735) of a TGMS line were dehulled, soaked in 75% ethanol for 1-3 s, and washed in running tap water for 10 min. Seeds were disinfected for 10 min in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution and then rinsed three times in sterile distilled water. The seeds were germinated in a 100-ml flask containing half strength Murashige and Skoog's (MS) (1962) medium with 0.6% agar and 1.5% sucrose. Shoot base segments (5 mm long) were excised under aseptic conditions from 2-wk-old seedlings. They were then cultured in flasks containing about 5.0 ml of agar-solidified MS medium supplemented with 2 mg benzylaminopurine (BAP)/liter and grown under 10/14-h light/dark (L/D) photoperiod at 25 °C. After 4 wk of culture, proliferated shoots were counted, and then subcultured under the same conditions. The solidified MS medium with 0.1 mg naphthalene acetic acid (NAA)/liter was used for rooting.